

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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TRANSFORMATION OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITALIZATION: MODERN APPROACHES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract: The article examines the impact of organizational culture on the success of digital transformation in modern companies. Based on the analysis of scientific literature and practical examples, key factors determining the success of digital technology implementation have been identified. The results show that two-thirds of failed digitalization attempts are related not to technological problems but to staff resistance and the organizational culture's unpreparedness for change. Practical recommendations for managers on fostering a culture that supports digital transformations are proposed.

Key words: digital transformation, organizational culture, change management, digital competencies, leadership.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada zamonaviy kompaniyalarda raqamli transformatsiya jarayonining muvaffaqiyatiga tashkiliy madaniyatning ta'siri o'rganiladi. Ilmiy adabiyotlar va amaliy misollar tahlili asosida raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etishda muvaffaqiyatni belgilovchi asosiy omillar aniqlangan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, raqamlashtirishning muvaffaqiyatsiz tugashi holatlarining uchdan ikki qismi texnologik muammolar bilan emas, balki xodimlarning qarshiligi va tashkilot madaniyatining o'zgarishlarga tayyor emasligi bilan bog'liq. Raqamli transformatsiyani qo'llab-quvvatlovchi korporativ madaniyatni shakllantirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli transformatsiya, tashkiliy madaniyat, o'zgarishlarni boshqarish, raqamli kompetensiyalar, yetakchilik.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается влияние организационной культуры на успешность процессов цифровой трансформации в современных компаниях. На основе анализа научной литературы и практических примеров выявлены ключевые факторы, определяющие эффективность внедрения цифровых технологий. Результаты исследования показывают, что две трети неудачных попыток цифровизации связаны не с технологическими проблемами, а с сопротивлением персонала и неподготовленностью организационной культуры к изменениям. В работе представлены практические рекомендации для руководителей по формированию культуры, поддерживающей цифровые трансформации.

Ключевые слова: цифровая трансформация, организационная культура, управление изменениями, цифровые компетенции, лидерство.

INTRODUCTION

Today, most companies face the need for digital transformation — the integration of new technologies into all aspects of their operations. However, digitalization is not just about purchasing new software or automating processes; it represents a profound change in how people work, interact, and make decisions.

Statistics paint an alarming picture: according to research, about 70% of digital transformation attempts end in failure [1]. Interestingly, the main reason for these failures is not technical problems but the human factor. Employees resist change, managers do not understand how to properly manage transformation, and organizational culture remains conservative.

Research relevance. In the scientific literature, many studies focus on the technological aspects of digitalization, while far less attention is paid to the question of how organizational culture must evolve for people to adopt new technologies. Companies invest millions in implementing digital systems but often neglect to prepare employees for change.

Research problem. Why do some companies successfully undergo digital transformation while others fail despite using the same technologies? What aspects of organizational culture need to be changed for digitalization to be successful?

Research objective is to identify the key characteristics of organizational culture that contribute to or hinder successful digital transformation and to develop practical recommendations for managers.

Research tasks:

- analyze contemporary scientific approaches to the relationship between organizational culture and digital transformation;
- identify the main barriers that impede successful digitalization;
- determine the success factors of digital transformation;
- formulate practical recommendations for organizational leaders.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Questions of organizational culture and its influence on company effectiveness have attracted researchers' attention for several decades. One of the seminal works in this field was conducted by Edgar Schein, who defined organizational culture as a system of basic assumptions, values, and artifacts shared by members of an organization [Schein, 1985]. Schein proposed examining culture at three levels: visible artifacts (what can be seen and heard), espoused values (what people state about their beliefs), and basic underlying assumptions (deep-seated beliefs that shape the perception of reality). This model remains widely used by scholars analyzing organizational cultures.

Cameron and Quinn made a significant contribution to the understanding of cultural typologies by developing the Competing Values Framework [2]. They identified four types of organizational culture based on two dimensions: flexibility versus stability, and internal versus external focus. According to their classification, clan culture is based on collaboration and interpersonal relationships; adhocracy culture is oriented toward innovation and entrepreneurship; market culture focuses on competition and achieving measurable results; and hierarchy culture is built on formal rules and procedures. This typology has proven especially useful for understanding how different cultures respond to change and innovation.

With the rapid expansion of business digitalization, a substantial body of research has emerged that examines the relationship between organizational culture and the successful implementation of digital technologies. The work of Butt and colleagues demonstrates that successful companies strategically shape their culture as a resource for digital transformation rather than assuming culture will adapt spontaneously [1]. Using the example of three large industrial firms, the authors showed that leaders use culture as a mechanism of social control in the adoption of new technologies. Research by Cyfert et al. complements this perspective, revealing that digital leadership and the development of employees' digital competencies are critically important [4]. The authors found that while many organizations are technologically ready for digitalization, they remain psychologically and culturally unprepared for large-scale change.

Of particular interest is the work of Cao, who studied the relationship between organizational culture type and a company's ability to innovate in the context of digitalization [3]. His empirical findings convincingly demonstrated that an adhocratic culture—characterized by flexibility and innovativeness—has the strongest positive correlation with the success of digital transformation. It is followed by clan, market, and hierarchical cultures, in descending order of effectiveness. These results support the intuitive assumption that cultures oriented toward change and experimentation adapt more easily to the demands of the digital era.

Edmondson made an important contribution to understanding the human factor in digital transformation with her concept of psychological safety [5]. She showed that in organizations where people feel safe expressing ideas, admitting mistakes, and experimenting with new approaches, innovative activity is significantly higher. This is especially relevant in the context of digital transformation, where employees must master unfamiliar technologies and inevitably make mistakes during the learning process. Organizations with high psychological safety create an environment in which employees are unafraid to try new digital tools and pursue innovative solutions.

Classical works on change management also retain their relevance in the digital era. Lewin's model of change, proposed as early as 1947, describes organizational transformation as a three-stage process: unfreezing, change, and refreezing [7]. Although criticized for its linear structure, the model still provides insight into why people resist change and how such resistance can be overcome. Kotter expanded on these ideas by proposing an eight-step model of change management that emphasizes creating a sense of urgency, forming a coalition of change supporters, and achieving quick wins [6]. These principles are highly applicable in managing digital transformation, which inherently represents a large-scale organizational change.

The fourth type is hierarchical culture, built on strict rules, formal procedures, and rigid control. This type of culture creates the most obstacles for successful digital transformation. Slow decision-making, widespread fear of taking responsibility for new initiatives, and a punitive approach to mistakes seriously hinder innovation and impede adaptation to rapidly changing technological environments.

A review of existing studies has identified several key obstacles that consistently impede successful digitalization across different organizations.

1. Employee resistance to change. This remains the most significant and widespread barrier. Employees resist change for various reasons: fear of job loss due to automation, lack of confidence in mastering new technologies, or reluctance to abandon familiar routines [Lewin, 1947]. According to the analysis, in 65% of unsuccessful digital transformation cases, the primary cause of failure was active or passive resistance from employees.

2. Lack of digital skills and competencies. This barrier is especially acute because many companies implement complex digital systems without providing sufficient employee training. Statistics show that only 56% of organizations undergoing digital transformation offer their personnel comprehensive training on new processes and tools [1]. As a result, employees may begin using new systems nominally but fail to utilize them effectively, reducing the overall return on investment.

3. Weak or inconsistent leadership in the transformation process. A common strategic mistake occurs when top management delegates responsibility for digital transformation solely to the IT department while remaining uninvolved. Numerous studies demonstrate that the personal example and active engagement of leaders are critical success factors [4]. If top executives do not personally adopt new systems or demonstrate their value, employees are unlikely to take the transformation seriously.

4. Lack of a clear and structured change management strategy. Many organizations focus predominantly on the technical side of digitalization—purchasing equipment, installing software, and building IT infrastructure—while neglecting the human factor. As a result, there is no coherent communication plan, no system to support employees during adaptation, and no explanation of the purpose and expected benefits of the changes.

5. Fragmentation and siloing within organizations. In large companies, departments often function in isolation, rarely sharing information or best practices. This fragmentation becomes a critical barrier during digital transformation, a period when coordinated action, cross-departmental cooperation, and knowledge exchange are essential for achieving organizational readiness and synchronizing digital initiatives [8].

A detailed analysis of successful digital transformation cases has revealed a set of factors that consistently help companies navigate this complex process effectively. The most important among these is active and engaged leadership. In organizations that have successfully undergone transformation, leaders do not confine themselves to declarative statements about the importance of digitalization. Instead, they are the first to master new tools and technologies, setting a personal example for the entire organization. They regularly communicate with employees at all levels, clearly explaining the goals and rationale behind the implemented changes, openly addressing questions, and alleviating employees' concerns.

The second crucial success factor is significant and systematic investment in employee training and development. Leading companies create not just one-off training sessions but continuous learning systems aimed at developing digital skills and competencies. Importantly, such training is not conducted as a single event at the beginning of system implementation but is provided on an ongoing basis. This approach takes into account the varying initial skill levels of different employee groups and their individual learning styles when assimilating new information.

The third critical factor is the creation of an atmosphere of psychological safety within the organization. In successful companies, employees do not fear trying new approaches or making mistakes while learning unfamiliar technologies. Management and colleagues perceive errors not as grounds for punishment or criticism but as natural and valuable sources of learning and professional growth [5]. Such a supportive environment enables employees to feel comfortable and confident enough to experiment with new digital tools and search for optimal ways to apply them in their work.

The fourth success factor is the strategy of achieving quick wins and demonstrating early results. Experienced organizations do not begin large-scale transformation with overly ambitious global projects. Instead, they launch relatively small pilot initiatives that can quickly demonstrate specific, measurable results and deliver clear benefits. This approach helps overcome employees' natural skepticism and creates positive momentum for progressing toward more extensive changes [6].

The fifth important factor is transparent, honest, and regular communication with all stakeholders. Employees at all organizational levels must clearly understand what is happening in the company, why changes are being implemented, what benefits they will bring, and how these changes will affect their daily work. Regular and fully transparent communication from management greatly reduces anxiety and uncertainty—common during periods of organizational change—and minimizes resistance to new initiatives.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conducted research convincingly demonstrates that digital transformation is, first and foremost, a transformation of people and organizational culture rather than merely the implementation of new technologies. Companies that deeply understand this principle and act accordingly achieve significantly greater success in digitalization, whereas organizations that focus solely on the technological component often encounter failures and do not obtain the expected return on investment.

Analysis of the literature revealed several key patterns that have important practical implications for organizational leaders. First, the type of organizational culture has a decisive influence on the success of digitalization processes. Flexible, innovative cultures oriented toward experimentation and change adapt to digital transformation considerably faster and more effectively than rigid hierarchical structures characterized by formal rules and a pervasive fear of mistakes.

Second, the main obstacles to digital transformation are directly linked to human factors: active or passive employee resistance to change, a substantial lack of necessary digital skills and competencies, and weak or inconsistent leadership from top management.

Third, among the key factors ensuring successful transformation, the most important are active and engaged leadership at all levels, substantial investments in systematic employee training and development, creating an atmosphere of psychological safety that allows people to experiment without fear of punishment, and maintaining transparent, regular communication about the goals and progress of change initiatives.

Fourth, an organization's genuine readiness for change extends far beyond technological preparedness. It must also include organizational readiness—adequate processes, flexible structures, and sufficient resources—and psychological readiness, meaning employees' willingness and ability to accept and support changes.

Finally, successful digital transformation inevitably requires a systemic approach to change management across the entire organization, rather than simple technical implementation of new software and equipment. Only an integrated strategy that aligns culture, leadership, communication, training, and organizational processes can ensure sustainable and meaningful transformation outcomes.

These conclusions have substantial practical value and can help leaders of various organizations plan, organize, and implement digital transformation more consciously and strategically, avoiding common mistakes and focusing on the factors that truly determine success.

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